

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D6.6 Policy Briefings v2

WP6 - Dissemination and
Communication

Version: 1

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CNR	National Research Council Italy
CRUI	Conference of Rectors of Italian Universities
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
ECE NTUA	National Technical University of Athens – School of Electrical and Computing Engineering
EDC	Equality and Diversity Committee
EPB	Ecole Polytechnique de Bruxelles
FUNCOM	Collaboration with Fundraising and Communication Department
GE	Gender Equality
GEC	Gender Equality Committee
GMUS	Grant Management Unified Electronic System
HE	Higher Education
HR	Human Resources
iGEP	Inclusive Gender Equality Plan
IRB	Institute for Research in Biomedicine

PR (office)	Public Relations
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
R&I	Research & Innovation
SRNSFG	Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
STU BA	Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
ToR	Terms of Reference
UEFISCDI	Executive Unit for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles
UNILE	Salento university
UZG FER	University of Zagreb – Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing
WIN event	Women in INnovation
(GEP) WG	Working Group
WP	Work Packages
YU	Yasar University

Executive Summary

The D6.6 “Policy Briefings v2” which is part of Task 6.4: Development of Policy briefings and final conference, includes a European and nine national policy briefings developed in collaboration by VIL and the CALIPER’s RPOs/RFOs respectively. For each of the policy briefings the rationale behind their development is explained.

The primary target audience of the CALIPER policy briefings is the staff and management of Higher Education Institutions, RPOs and RFOs, staff and management of governmental bodies, and agencies in charge of Gender Equality, Higher Education, and R&I at European, regional and national level. Policymakers are the secondary target audience as well. Last but not least, the document can be used as a guide and practical tool for other “Horizon2020”/ “Horizon Europe” consortia aiming at achieving structural changes towards gender equality.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

Within CALIPER's time span, and in three different "versions", nine policy briefings at national level and one at European level have been/will be developed. In each of the three versions, each of the CALIPER's participating RPOs/RFOs (GEP implementing partners) in collaboration with VIL developed/will develop one national and one European policy briefing respectively aspiring to link Research and Innovation with gender equality. The policy briefings and thus the present deliverable aim to reflect the ongoing findings and the experience gained during the CALIPER's lifetime in relation to the development and implementation of inclusive GEPs in seven RPOs and two RFOs focused on STEM fields.

This deliverable D6.6 Policy briefing v2 is the second version of policy briefings that CALIPER project develops. Each of the three policy briefing versions is following a specific thematic area according to the progress of the project and the stages for a GEP development and implementation. The list below describes the focus areas of each of the policy briefing "versions":

- 1st version: Policy briefing v1: Focusing on the design and development of a GEP
- 2nd version: Policy briefing v2: Focusing on the implementation of a GEP
- 3rd version: Policy briefing v3: Focusing on the evaluation and assessment of a GEP

The present deliverable D6.6 Policy briefing v2, is aimed at European and national (in Croatian, Greek, Georgian, Italian, Belgian, Spanish, Romanian, and Turkish) stakeholders who are implementing equality measures in their institution such change agents in HE institutions, public/private organisation, RPO/RFOs, HR professionals, top and middle management and researchers including also potentially policymakers at European and national level.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The structure of the deliverable is the following: Chapter 1 introduces the purpose and scope of the present deliverable along with its linkages with other WPs and Tasks. Chapter 2 describes the methodology that was followed to develop the national and European policy briefings ensuring coherence among the project partners. Chapter 3 presents the policy briefings developed at the European and national levels by VIL and each RPO/RFO respectively. A total of 10 briefings are included in this deliverable. Chapter 4 includes a few final remarks on the deliverable and provides some more information about the upcoming policy briefings (3rd version).

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This deliverable is part of Task 6.4: Development of Policy briefings and final conference of WP6 Dissemination and Communication, aiming at producing key policy briefings to reflect the findings and experiences gained during the project's lifetime. This task contributes to T5.3 Raising awareness and engagement activities and T5.4 Sustaining and replicating in STEM as these tasks aimed at creating a favourable environment for accepting and sustaining the GEPs. Furthermore, it contributes to T6.3 External communication and multiplying effect.

Last but not least, this deliverable is interlinked with, WP3 implementation of GEPs, and WP4 Monitoring and Evaluation given that it draws its content from these work packages.

2 Policy briefings' approach

2.1 Policy briefings' aim

The second version of the CALIPER policy briefings serves as practical evidence of the GEP implementation process at each GEP implementing partner, transferring the knowledge that the CALIPER consortium has gained so far via the structural change process that has been introduced after the implementation of the first iteration phase of the gender equality measures foreseen in their approved GEP.

It provides to the target audience with tips on how to successfully implement a GEP (European policy briefing) and with an overview of the activities implemented so far along with the resources needed including also key enabling factors and main challenges identified and the overall impact of the action at the respective institution (national policy briefings) with an overall aim to facilitate the implementation/adoption of the respective gender equality strategies of other research performing institutions and thus having as a project wider impact.

After the approval of each version of the briefings from the European Commission, the content of the briefings will be transferred into shorter and easy to read templates for their dissemination. These templates will be appealing with schemes and note boxes to present the information in a more intriguing way. The final versions will be uploaded on the CALIPER website, and will be disseminated through the CALIPER social channels, as well as the partners channels. The policy briefings may be potentially translated into each RPO/RFOs national language, to increase the engagement of the national target audience.

2.2 Policy briefings' target audience

The policy briefing is an action-oriented tool targeting practitioners interested and/or active in a specific policy domain, in this case, related to Gender Equality in R&I.

The primary target audience of the CALIPER policy briefings is the staff and management of Higher Education Institutions, RPOs and RFOs, staff and management of governmental bodies, and agencies in charge of Gender Equality, Higher Education, and R&I at European, regional, and national level. Policymakers are the secondary target audience as well. Last but not least, the document can be used as a guide and practical tool for other "Horizon2020" / "Horizon Europe" consortia aiming at achieving structural changes towards gender equality.

2.3 CALIPER policy briefings' structure

Both the European and national policy briefings were created based on the CALIPER experience of the first iteration phase of the GEPs implementation. The European policy briefing includes three parts: 1. an executive summary which briefly makes a reference to the added value of the briefing, to trigger the reader's interest 2. The main part, which contains a list of recommendations for a successful GEP implementation drawn upon the collective experience of the CALIPER partners after the finalisation of the first iteration of their GEP implementation and 3. A conclusion and the next steps prepare the reader for the upcoming policy briefing.

All national policy briefings share the same structure for the sake of consistency, and for facilitating the dissemination of the briefings on a national level. In particular, they include four parts: The first part is the executive summary triggering the reader's interest in the briefing, and the second part describes the GEP implementation process followed by the CALIPER project. In the third and main part of the policy briefing,

the implemented gender equality actions included in the GEP of each RPO/RFO are presented, and divided into the specific focus areas, as they have been identified in their GEPs. This section provides a description of the specific actions that have been implemented during the respective period, and for each action, the briefing presents a description of the action, the required resources, the key enabling factors and the main challenges, and the impact of the action at the institution. The fourth part includes the next steps in preparing the reader for the upcoming policy briefing.

3 CALIPER's policy briefings

This chapter contains the 10 policy briefings that the CALIPER project has developed within the second version of policy briefings. First, the European briefing is presented, followed by the nine national briefings from the seven RPOs and two RFOs participating in the project.

3.1 European Policy Briefing

Executive summary

The present policy briefing is focused on providing key recommendations for a successful GEP implementation process to relevant stakeholders who are implementing gender equality measures at their institutions drawing inspiration from the CALIPER partners' experience and their journey during the first iteration phase of their GEPs implementation.

CALIPER Recommendations for a successful GEP implementation process

The CALIPER project, following the steps of the GEAR tool, has structured its methodology in five interlinked phases for setting up and implementing the GEP in the partner institutions. Focusing on the GEP implementation, the CALIPER project foresees this process at its participating RPO/RFOs in two iteration phases with a duration of twelve months each. After the end of each iteration phase, the results are analysed through a performance monitoring process, leading to the redesign and refinement of the GEP actions to better fit the needs of the institution.

At this point, the CALIPER partners have just concluded the implementation of the first iteration phase of their GEP implementation and the section below provides a list of recommendations that can facilitate the implementation of a GEP based on the CALIPER partners' experience so far.

Recommendations:

Take advantage of the European policy landscape: In 2021 the European Commission introduced the Gender Equality plans as a mandatory eligibility criterion for public institutions to obtain research funds via the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme. The experience of the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs have shown that leveraging this policy framework facilitated the process for the official adoption of the GEP and the implementation of the respective actions foreseen.

Take advantage of the national policy landscape: National regulations very often follow the European direction and can directly or indirectly influence the process of adopting and implementing a GEP. In some of the CALIPER partners' countries, during the development and implementation phases of their GEPs, national regulations were approved that facilitated their work. Below some examples are described:

Greece (ECE NTUA): Law 4589/2019 (Article 33) stipulates the creation of University Gender Equality Committees (GECs), as advisory bodies of the University Senate, and the administrations of the Schools and Departments. In particular, the NTUA GEC facilitated the implementation of the GEP at the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering. The GEC has been present in almost all relevant collaborative activities (either implemented or designed) contributing to the wider dissemination and impact of the actions. In addition, Law 4808/2021 which puts into force a framework to prevent, and combat violence and harassment, comprises a facilitating tool and argument for the implementation of the respective GEP actions foreseen in the GEP such as the Establishment of formal procedures to handle incidents of bias and sexist behaviour in the working environment and establishment of a formal mechanism dealing with cases of sexual harassment.

Italy (UNILE): The European Commission has provided indications on the implementation of the GEP, reported by the CRUI (“conference of rectors of Italian universities”) in the “Vademecum for the development of the Gender Equality Plan in Italian Universities”, with the aim of providing an operational tool to facilitate the drafting of the Plan. The latter was elaborated by a technical board nominated by the CRUI and officially released on the 7th of October 2021, supporting the structuring and implementation of the UNILE GEP.

Spain (IRB): The Royal Decree 901/2020 (13/10/2020) which regulates equality plans and their registration and modifies Royal Decree 713/2010, of May 28, on the registration and deposit of agreements and collective labour agreements and the Royal Decree 902/2020, (13/10/2020) which regulates equal pay for men and women influenced the evolution and planning of the GEP, since they delivered a series of requirements and compliance factors that were taken into consideration when developing relevant actions.

Belgium (ULB): ULB’s GEP includes a measure for the launch of an Action-oriented study “Feasibility of affirmative actions for academic recruitment”, in cooperation with ULB’s Equality Law Clinic. This is an organisation that belongs to the University, that allows students to deepen their legal skills while contributing concretely to the promotion of social justice, equality and fundamental rights, by working for the benefit of disadvantaged or excluded groups, according to an approach combining the local and the global. During this action, a national decree (crafted in 2010) was discovered, which could allow for the implementation of affirmative actions in higher education institutions in the French-speaking community of Belgium. The law is not in force yet and is pending approval. The university is in the process to develop a high-level strategy to enlarge its impact- by seeking to positively affect, advocate and lobby at the political level, to speed up the process for application of the law. If successful, ULB’s action could contribute to progressing a regulatory framework and needed legal backing, to smoothly implement affirmative action at an institutional level, while also positively impacting gender equality in the national policy landscape of the French speaking community in Belgium.

Secure the top management’s support: A successful GEP needs the active involvement and commitment of the top management. Already from the design and development phase of the GEP, it is vital to have in the team representatives from the top management. This way, the approval processes will be faster, and the proposed structural changes will have higher chances to be adopted and sustained. For ensuring that the top management is on board, present concrete actions with specific goals and timelines and demonstrate what will be the structural impact of the action to the institution.

Adopt a bottom-up approach: In cases of resistance from the top management that can cause delays to the overall timeline for the GEP implementation, it is crucial to secure the support of the employees. Engage them in the GEP implementation process for creating a gender friendly culture within the institution that will motivate the internal staff and eventually function as pressure points for the top management.

Take care of your resources: Each action requires its own resources in terms of personnel, budget, time, and infrastructure. Planning the needed resources for the implementation of each GEP action is vital. Overspending or underspending resources on a specific action can compromise the success of the action and the GEP in general.

Keep it simple: The GEP should cover a wide range of areas, but the actions in each area should be clear and justified. If there are actions that have many similarities in terms of objectives or implementation process, the responsible team should consider merging the actions to save resources and keep the engagement high.

Go for the “quick wins” first: The GEP actions can be categorised as soft or structural. By soft measures we mean those measures which do not impact the structure of the organisation itself (yet), and are usually shorter-term, preparatory measures, aimed at building preconditions for institutional change. On the contrary, structural measures are those actions/provisions that change the institutional structure, rules and procedures of the organisation and are therefore medium-long term and even permanent measures. In this regard, the soft actions are easier to be implemented, meet less resistance, and can help the institution develop a culture of gender equality. These actions prepare the ground for the internal environment, to discuss and approve the structural actions. Therefore, starting with “soft” actions, and collaborating with people that are already involved in the GEP could facilitate the process, particularly within research organizations that are at a starting stage in terms of GE policies-actions. Complex actions that need people from different departments or influence the structural processes need more time to be organised and executed.

Bear in mind potential delays: It is expected to meet some delays, either because of resistance or simply due to the workload of the involved people. In addition, structural actions demand more time and resources to be implemented. These actions require the official approval of the top management through councils and board meetings. These meetings take place at specific times throughout the year, which means that the actions might need to be on hold until the next meeting to be approved. Having this in mind, submitting the proposals early and knowing the timeline of the top management meetings is a significant factor to approve actions on time. In many cases, the procedures can take longer than expected and this can cause delays in the whole GEP implementation process. Set realistic timelines for the implementation of the actions, taking into consideration potential delays and resistances.

Collaborate with external actors: external support can facilitate the GEP implementation internally and at the same time: internal change agents get the opportunity to exchange knowledge by actively involving external actors in the process. Management structures can be motivated towards GE Policies when they acknowledge that this policy agenda is shared by a variety of entities and can be conducive to new collaborations and/or strengthening existing ones. Furthermore, by creating ties with your local innovation ecosystem, the actions can become more sustainable, if human and financial resources are pooled on specific actions that promote gender equality in R&I.

Awareness raising activities are important: one of the most important steps during the process of implementing a GEP is to secure the support of the internal and external stakeholders. A lack of knowledge of gender equality basic concepts and framework is often reported by GE working groups in Research Organisation, particularly those that are at a starting stage. Therefore, setting up awareness raising actions can be of use: internally, this will facilitate and strengthen the commitment from the internal staff to the implementation of the approved actions. Externally, the awareness raising activities, will engage external stakeholders, such as other institutions and give the opportunity for knowledge exchange and collaborative activities to be made.

Conclusion and next steps

The present policy briefing provides the reader with “tips” and advice based on the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs experience so far, on how to successfully implement the gender equality measures included in their GEPs.

This policy briefing is the second out of the three to be developed: the first one was using the knowledge and experience gained from the project more specifically on setting up inclusive GEPs; this document focuses on their implementation, while and monitoring and evaluating an inclusive GEP will be the subject of the 3rd policy briefing.

While CALIPER RPOs/RFOs continue with the second iteration phase of their GEP implementation, the third policy briefing will be developed and published based on the new knowledge generated by the GEPs' evaluation process upon conclusion of the implementation phase. The third policy briefing will be published at the end of the project, in December 2023.

3.2 National Policy Briefings

All national briefings, share the same executive summary, the same methodology and the same conclusion to secure consistency among the national policy briefings. This section begins with the common sections to be included in each national briefing namely the executive summary methodology and conclusion and then continues with the main part of the briefings per partner. This has been done to avoid repetition in each partner's section in the present document. The common sections will be transferred at each partner briefing when the present deliverable will be accepted by the EC and the briefings will be transferred to appealing templates for their dissemination.

Executive summary

The recent adoption of the GEP as an eligibility criterion set by the European Commission for research organisations to access the European fundings sped up the process of mainstreaming gender in public institutions. In the context of CALIPER, the RPOs/RFOs have designed and developed their inclusive GEPs and now are in the implementation process, consisting of two distinct iteration phases. At this point, the first iteration phase is completed, and they are ready to share their experience during this process and inspire other institutions in their national context to follow their example and implement gender equality actions.

This briefing presents the CALIPER methodology for setting up and implementing a GEP. The main part includes the main actions implemented during the first iteration phase per partner, presenting the needed resources along with the key enabling factors and main challenges for their implementation as well as their impact so far.

The CALIPER methodology

The CALIPER project, following the steps of the GEAR tool, set up its methodology in five interlinked phases to design, implement and evaluate the tailored GEPs for each participating RPO/RFO (9 in total). Following the internal and external assessment of the RPOs/RFOs to map the state of gender equality internally and externally, their GEP was developed following a co-creation process with both internal and external actors. The CALIPER methodology foresees the GEP implementation at its participating RPO/RFOs in two iteration phases with a duration of twelve months each. After the end of each iteration phase, the results are analysed through Key Performance Indicators leading to the redesign and refinement of the GEP's actions, if deemed necessary.

One of the main bodies that have been created in the context of CALIPER, is the GEP working group (GEP WG), which is responsible for the implementation of all the project phases. The GEP WG consists of actors representing academic, managerial, and administrative staff. Also, the GEP WG, as the main supervisor, has been working on the implementation of the concrete measures foreseen. In addition, the R&I Hub, has been set up at the very beginning of the project, adopting a quadruple/multiple helix and a gender sensitive approach to innovation ecosystems, consisting of stakeholders from Academia, business, CSOs, and public institutions. The Hub secures the intersectoral character of the GEP actions through specific collaborative actions.

Conclusion

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

The present policy briefing describes the methodology of CALIPER with a focus on the first iteration phase of the GEP implementation, as well as the specific GEP actions that have been implemented in this regard for inspiring other national Research Performing Organisations to implement gender equality actions.

This policy briefing is the second out of the three to be developed by CALIPER using the knowledge and experience gained from the first iteration phase. The RPOs/RFOs continues with the second iteration phase of the GEP implementation, and the monitoring and evaluation of the respective actions included in its GEP. After the completion of the implementation phase, the third policy briefing will be developed and published including the knowledge gained from the overall evaluation process. This is anticipated to be published at the end of the project, in December 2023.

3.2.1 Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)

3.2.1.1. University of Zagreb – Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (FER – UZG)

Made by CALIPER: inspiring actions from UZG FER

In this section, the implemented gender equality actions included in the GEP of UZG FER will be presented, divided into specific thematic areas. During the first iteration phase, the actions that have been implemented belong to the areas of institutional governance, institutional communication, teaching and research, and student services. For each action, the briefing presents the *description of the action*, the *required resources*, the *key enabling factors* and the *main challenges*, and the *impact of the action*.

Institutional governance

Action 1: Pilot programme for the empowerment of female researchers

Description/scope of the action: The implementation of this measure provided specific professional development consulting for young female researchers and raised awareness around the barriers to the inclusion of women in research and innovation. The long-term goal of this measure is to remove these barriers and reduce the phenomenon, of the women being underrepresented in STEM fields.

Needed resources: Four people of the UZG FER CALIPER GEP WG coordinated the implementation of the action. The GEP WG of FER consists of actors representing academic, managerial, and administrative staff. It carried out the recruitment process of both the mentors and the mentees, (female doctoral and postdoctoral students), and provided technical support and evaluation of the program. In addition, the communication office was involved in this action for the promotion of the program on the institutional website. The action needed 11 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: This action was enabled by the commitment of the vice dean for research that is the supervisor of the overall GEP implementation. Also, the support of the external stakeholders, meaning the female mentors, was another factor that facilitated the successful implementation of the action. Not major challenges have been identified at the implementation of this action.

Impact of the action: UZG FER organised 4 online workshops involving an expert on gender equality and female managers (mentors) in industry and academia. Through the trainings, 11 female students were trained.

Action 2: Reporting on the institutional state of gender equality

Description/scope of the action: UZG FER established a system of collecting gender disaggregated data for all students and employees. The implementation of this measure aimed at establishing appropriate administrative mechanisms for collecting and analysing data and reporting on the status of gender equality.

Needed resources: The GEP WG covered the role of coordinating the activities to carry out, defining the different steps to take, and implementing the activities. All the data were collected, and a report was created in close collaboration with the following administrative offices: Students Services, Human Resources Office, Center for Research Support, and Central Library. The action needed 15 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The GEP WG had the support of the top management since they closely collaborated with the vice dean for research who is in charge of the process of implementation of the GEP. Not major challenges have been identified at the implementation of this action.

Impact of the action: New reports containing gender disaggregated data by different offices to be updated in biannual cycles were developed. It is foreseen that after the end of the CALIPER project, a permanent body promoting gender equality will be established, and it will be responsible for the reporting.

Institutional communication

Action 1: Establishment of a specialised digital communication channel

Description/scope of the action: The measure foresees the establishment of a digital communication and information channel (website) for the dissemination of relevant information on gender equality and the promotion of female researchers and their achievements. Communication campaigns were also implemented, e.g., on International Day of Women and Girls in Science, Girls in ICT Day, etc. In the long term, this measure aims to encourage and attract new female students at UZG FER, empower female students and researchers, and retain women in the higher education and science.

Needed resources: The GEP WG coordinated the activity. In addition, the support of the Center for information support and the Public Relations Office was necessary for setting up and updating the website with relevant information. The process was overseen by the vice dean for research. The action needed 13 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The team had the support of the top management since they closely collaborated with the vice dean for research who is in charge of the implementation of the GEP. The action didn't encounter any major challenges.

Impact of the action: A [permanent link](#) as part of the UZG FER's website was created, hosting information about the UZG FER GEP and their gender equality actions.

Teaching and research

Action 1: Integration of the gender dimension in teaching

Description/scope of the action: The measure envisaged a group of professors coming together to explore the possibility of integrating the gender dimension into the UZG FER's curriculum. In the long term, this measure aspires to integrate the gender dimension in research and innovation content.

Needed resources: The GEP WG had the overall responsibility of this activity and invited 10 professors to prepare the relevant material for the chosen courses. The action needed 20 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The support of the external stakeholders, meaning the professors, was a factor that facilitated the action. No major challenges were encountered.

Impact of the action: It will continue in the 2nd implementation phase when the developed material will be used to experimentally integrate the gender dimension in several courses.

Action 2: Promotion of the principles of gender equality in technology transfer

Description/scope of the action: The promotional activities aimed at the participation of female researchers in technology transfer and the promotion of gender equality towards external stakeholders. In the long term, the implementation of this measure aims at contributing to mainstreaming the gender equality principles in all aspects of cooperation with stakeholders in the innovation ecosystem and increase the number of projects incorporating the gender dimension.

Needed resources: The action was coordinated and carried out by the GEP WG in collaboration with the personnel of the Central Library and the Public relations office of the University. In total, 6 people were involved in the implementation of this activity. The action needed 10 months to be finalised

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The good collaboration between the GEP WG and the Central Library was a factor that enabled the implementation of the action. Also, external stakeholders including members of the R&I Hub participated in both days, as active speakers and also as spectators contributed to the efficient implementation of the action. No major challenges have been identified.

Impact of the action: In total, 8 R&I Hub members and their 15 employees accepted the invitation and participated in the event. About 30 FER students, employees, and alumni participated in the activities, which attracted over 200 visitors aged 5 to 90+.

Student services

Action 1: Attracting new students

Description/scope of the action: To attract new students to UZG FER, it is desirable to complement the existing activities with special events focusing on female students. Under this focus area and within the context of the WIN event two main activities implemented

- Filming a role model video with prof. emer. Branka Zovko Cihlar, first female professor at UZG-FER
- Programming workshop for girls (part of the WIN event)

Needed Resources: The GEP WG covered the role of coordinating the activities, defining the different steps, and implementing them. Also, the Public Relations Office provided support in communication activities. The programming workshop for girls was implemented with Stemalica, a member of the UZG FER R&I Hub. Also, amongst 20 workshop leaders, there were doctoral students of UZG-FER from the department for Control and Computer

The action attracted the most attention was programming workshops for children, implemented with the intention to attract more female students, which are currently underrepresented in the student body.

Engineering, and alumni of FER. The action needed 10 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The good collaboration between the GEP WG and the Central Library was a factor which promoted the implementation of the action. Also, the participation of the external stakeholders was another element that contributed to the success of the event. Not major challenges have been identified at the implementation of this action.

Impact of the action: In total 158 students at elementary schools participated in the 9 programming workshops, led and organised by 20 female students, employees and alumni of FER. A [Role model video](#) was produced as an episode of ŽensCast, a podcast of IEEE Women in Engineering.

3.2.1.2. Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (STU BA)

Made by CALIPER: Inspiring actions from STU BA

In the context of CALIPER, STU BA has designed and developed its inclusive GEP and now is in the process of its implementation. The University has set up a Gender Equality Strategy. Alignment between the STU BA GEP and the Gender Equality Strategy of the university will be sought. The fact that the CALIPER methodology is fully compliant and goes beyond the Horizon Europe basic requirement shall facilitate the process.

In this section, the implemented gender equality actions included in the GEP of STU BA will be presented, divided into specific thematic areas. During the first iteration phase, the actions that have been implemented belong to the areas of institutional governance, research, and teaching. For each action, the briefing presents the *description of the action*, the *required resources*, the *key enabling factors* and the *main challenges*, and the *impact of the action*.

Institutional governance

Action 1: Delegates

Description/scope of the action: This action created a network of delegates who will work on the area of gender equality activities at the faculty.

Needed resources: At the level of faculty management the action used employees within MTF STU interested in the topic of gender equality (Human Resources); at the level of financial budget the regular budget for HR activities is used. The action needed 11 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The main challenge of this action was the minimisation of costs associated with the original plan to establish a new position of a new vice dean for equal opportunities and gender equality. The enabling factor was the commitment of the Dean to complete the action and create the delegate network.

Impact of the action: The action brought structural change at the faculty.

Research

Action 1: Integration of the gender dimension in the final theses

Description/scope of the action: In the years 2017 to 2019, no research projects in the field of gender were carried out at MTF STU, and neither any diploma thesis or dissertation thesis included the topic of gender equality. This action motivated the students to include the gender aspect in their research work.

Needed resources: No additional resources were needed. Faculty employees and members of the project team participated in the action. External stakeholders were directly involved in the implementation of the present action and are directly affected. The action needed 24 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Internal communication between project team members and the Council for Gender Equality facilitated the action.

Impact of the action: The main impact is increased awareness of the issue of gender equality in the interaction between the student, the university, and the industry.

Action 2: Integration of the gender issues and the gender dimension into research projects

Description/scope of the action: This action contributes to promoting and disseminating gender equality. The topic is included in research projects and scientific articles. During the implementation phase of the GEP, two project proposals were made including the gender perspective.

Needed resources: The Council of Gender Equality was in charge of the action, in collaboration with the project team members. The action needed 24 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Internal communication between project team members and the Council for Gender Equality facilitated the action.

Impact of the action: The implementation of the GEP and the applied communication strategy resulted in an increase in the awareness and importance of gender equality at the faculty as a higher education institute as well as a research institute. By stabilising the internal culture in this area, there is an intersection between the professional STEM field and the issue of gender equality, which we demonstrate through the implementation of research projects.

Teaching

Action 1: Integration of the gender dimension in the curriculum

Description/scope of the action: The integration of gender in the curriculum should be implemented into existing syllabi and curricula of selected subject within MTF STU to include the issue of gender equality, as well as some selected topic/lectures in the curriculum.

Needed resources: Faculty employees and members of the project team participated in the action. The action needed 24 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: This action was successfully implemented, while the plan for the next academic year was also determined.

Impact of the action: Implementation is not conditional on compliance with the legislative order. It is part of internal awareness raising and maintaining internal culture. The action generated a curriculum involving the issue of gender equality. You can find information about the included lectures and their [overview](#). Students

acquire knowledge and skills that they transfer into practice and spread awareness, blurring the boundaries of the historical archaism about the nature of individual STEM occupations as exclusively male occupations.

3.2.1.3 Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB)

Made by CALIPER: Inspiring actions from ULB

The CALIPER Team is responsible for the implementation of all project phases and composed of - one professor in social psychology, one gender and equality officer, a full-time project manager and a periodic intern. The team as the main supervisor, project manager and leader of the GEP actions, has been working on the implementation of the concrete measures foreseen. Further, the Steering Committee is formed by members from the high and middle management of the University and the STEM faculties, actors and actresses of the University's gender policy and STEM representatives. It has a consultative and monitoring role (composed of 14 persons, 11 academics and 3 administrative: the 3 members of the CALIPER Team; the Vice Rector for gender & diversity; Dean of the faculty of sciences, Dean of EPB; 3 STEM faculty contact persons for gender policy, Director of the research department; University secretary; Director general of the University; Gender research structure co-directors). In addition, the R&I Hub, currently counts 33 representatives and is expected to grow.

In this section, the implemented actions of ULB will be presented, divided into the specific focus areas of their GEP. During the first iteration phase, the actions that have been implemented belong to the areas of human resources, institutional governance, research, and collaborative actions. For each action, the briefing presents the *description of the action*, the *required resources*, the *key enabling factors* and the *main challenges*, and the *impact of the action*.

Human resources

Action 1: Action oriented study: "Feasibility of affirmative actions for academic recruitment"

Description/scope of the action: The study 'Affirmative actions for academic recruitment' aimed at examining if affirmative actions (typology that includes quotas but also other types of measures) are feasible to be implemented at ULB from both a legal and an institutional perspective, as well as the consideration of which type of action would be the most appropriate to be implemented for improving the balance of women and men in the STEM academic body.

This action yielded effective results due to its collaborative nature, bringing in specialised expertise (of Equality Law Clinic) to thoroughly evaluate possibilities and advantages of different actions, at both European and more localised national level.

Needed resources: At this stage, resources used for the implementation of this action were exclusively human resources. Three students created the content which had been supervised by the Equality Law Clinic. The action needed 5 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The Collaboration with the students and the drawing on expertise of the Equality Law Clinic enabled the successful implementation of this action. The students who participated in this project were also very committed. No major challenges were reported.

Impact of the action: The legal study was carried out by ULB Equality Law Clinic. The result of the feasibility study about affirmative action provided the CALIPER team with a lot of new information about the legal framework to implement affirmative action at ULB and within an EU law context, operating at the European, national, and French-speaking community levels. Moreover, it led to the discovery of a law crafted to allow for the implementation of affirmative action which exists since 2010, but for which the implementation order is currently still missing in the French-speaking community of Belgium (which is responsible for upper education). The law is in place, but not applied yet. It is the chance for CALIPER and ULB to enlarge its ambitions and impact by seeking to positively influence, advocate and lobby at the political level, for a speeding up of the process for application of the law. Although a long road ahead, if the action is successful, this would mean the approval of a framework creating the needed legal backing to smoothly implement affirmative action at any institutional level, while also enabling CALIPER to positively impact gender equality in the national policy landscape of the French-speaking community in Belgium at large.

Institutional governance

Action 1: Gender+ commission in STEM faculties

Description/scope of the action: In order to institutionalise the gender+ policy at the STEM faculty level, a gender+ commission is established at each STEM faculty. The commissions are gradually involved in the implementation and monitoring of the current GEP actions to ensure the sustainability of the gender+ policy initiated by CALIPER after the finalisation of the project.

Needed resources: At this stage, resources used for the implementation of the action were exclusively human resources and include the members of the gender+ commissions. The CALIPER Team, together with two STEM deans, defined the mission of the future gender+ commissions. The action needed 4 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The involvement of the top management of the faculty facilitated the creation of the gender+ commissions. No resistance was reported.

In each of the two STEM faculties, this action enabled the project to not only create a sounding board and action-oriented group involved in key activities taking place across CALIPER, but also stipulated the emergence of a network of supporters and advocacy for gender equality across the science faculties.

Impact of the action: The gender+ Commissions already carried out 1 main action of the GEP (measure Gender target in STEM PhD juries), and they are working on several other GEP actions.

Action 2: Proposal for gender balanced participation in the Advisory Boards

Description/scope of the action: The action consists of a proposal for a pilot for gender-balanced composition of the Advisory Boards. The team targeted five advisory boards, linked to CALIPER's project goals, as a pilot action. This measure will help to evaluate the efficacy of the implementation and lay the foundations to make a balanced participation applicable to all advisory boards.

This action, by targeting several internal bodies and key advisory boards at institutional level, can be considered a key structural measure in the project – carrying the potential for systemic impact, to equal the scales for women at the leadership and decision-making level. It also bears the potential to surface institutional resistances.

Needed resources: The CALIPER Team and the CALIPER researcher did first an analysis of the composition of all advisory boards at ULB. They leveraged from the “ULB Annual Gender Report” from 2018 to 2021. The action needed 12 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: When implementing these changes of structural nature, the CALIPER team worked proactively and collaboratively to mitigate challenges in the implementation and alleviate any internal hesitations or concerns on the end of some actors linked to the feasibility of the measure. After an extended approval process, a successful and unanimous buy-in by top management for the proposal was achieved, by recalibrating certain aspects, making the plan more adaptable in response to unique needs of specific situations, to simplify the implementation across different faculty contexts.

Concretely in response to challenges, the CALIPER team wrote an abstract (½ pages) summarising and condensing main points and goals of the pilot project, revised the presentation of the pilot, created a presentation of annexes and some important arguments about why the action was critical. CALIPER researchers also proposed to work directly with and provide support to the presidents of the advisory boards targeted, to help them implement the action.

Impact of the action: The academic council approved the proposal for the creation of a pilot project targeting five key advisory boards. The institution began to work on the subject and this measure initiated reflection about the subject as well as consultations and discussions, that if the pilot is successful and positively evaluated, an approach for the reformation of further/all Advisory Boards across the university could be rolled out.

Research

Action 1: Gender target in STEM PhD juries

Description/scope of the action: This action aimed to stimulate the awareness about the low presence of women in STEM PhD juries of the EPB (Ecole polytechnique) and the Science faculty by establishing a gender target. Targets are “inspirational” goals, not a mandatory quota, but a recommendation to improve the composition of PhD juries and make them as gender-balanced as possible. External scholars must also be part of PhD juries. Therefore, targets can encourage PhD commissions to identify and invite external female scholars.

The action stimulates greater awareness on the underrepresentation of women therein. A key factor to successfully overcome carriers was that actors at different levels worked hand in hand on the conceptualisation and launch of the measure.

Needed resources: The CALIPER team together with top management representatives from both STEM faculties created together 2 Gender+ commissions (one in each of the STEM faculties: EPB & Sciences) which were responsible for drafting the proposal. The action to create a target in the EPB needed 9 months to be finalised. Further action will continue into iteration phase 2, to fully establish the target in the Science Faculty.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The EPB dean occupying a seat in the gender+ commission of his faculty for top level support, alongside the participation of the CALIPER Team, strengthened conjoint efforts in the successful, smooth, and full implementation of the gender target across the EPB’s faculty. For implementation in the Science Faculty, the CALIPER team is smoothing out shortcomings in feasibility, linked to a lack of internally available women in the faculty to occupy jury positions, creating a practical challenge around the seamless implementation of the target.

Impact of the action: The action increased awareness about the lack of women participating in STEM Ph.D. juries, triggering lively internal discussions in each STEM faculty. This proposal led to a tangible increase of the number of women in STEM Ph.D. juries. At the EPB faculty, all Ph.D. juries from this year included a women expert.

Collaborative actions

Action 1: WIN event: Joint ULB-g4g event

Description/scope of the action: The main objective of this event was to bring young girls in their formidable years (12-15 years old) closer to STEM subjects and encourage them in future possibilities. Around 100 girls participated in 4 workshops, during a full day of hands on STEM exploration, to build their confidence and belonging in STEM, while meeting and interacting with the inspiring stories of local STEM role models.

Needed resources: The main organisers and key stakeholders of the action were CALIPER and g4g's Project Manager, the EPB, the communication manager of ULB, the ULB R&I Hub, the ULB science laboratories, communication managers from the science faculties, and 2 students as technical support. The action needed 3 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The collaboration with an NGO specialised in encouraging a future generation of female scientists and leaders, together with the participation of both the EPB and science faculty, and exceptional resources (both human and technical) provided by the R&I Hub, were the key facilitators of the action. The main challenge for the timely implementation of the action were existing COVID-19 restrictive measures, causing a delay in the launch date of the event.

Impact of the action: The WIN (g4g day at ULB) event took place on the 30th of April 2022. The action engaged a great number of female students - approximately 100 students mainly between 12 and 15 years old from diverse socio-economic backgrounds, as well as a dedicated pool of over 80 volunteers and role models from diverse industry, academic and civil society backgrounds. The young girls enjoyed the activities, with close to 90% of them being more interested in pursuing sciences after partaking in the event.

3.2.1.4 National Technical University of Athens – School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE NTUA)

Made by CALIPER: Inspiring actions from ECE NTUA

In this section, the implemented actions of ECE NTUA will be presented, divided into the specific focus areas of their GEP. During the first iteration phase, the actions that have been implemented belong to the areas of human resources, institutional governance, institutional communication, teaching and student services, intersectionality, and collaborative actions. For each action, the briefing presents the *description of the action*, the *required resources*, the *key enabling factors* and the *main challenges*, and the *impact of the action*.

The ECE NTUA GEP WG, as the main supervisor, has been working on the implementation of the concrete measures foreseen. It consists of representatives from various School staff categories (academics, administrative personnel, researchers (tenured and non tenured), technical personnel etc.), while its total members are currently 16.

Human resources

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Action 1: Implementation of a framework for working conditions of researchers in the ECE NTUA

Description/scope of the action: The action refers to the drafting of a framework named “Post Doc Research Guide” including measures and recommendations to improve work-life balance and social security for non-tenured researchers, creating a friendlier environment for the people that have children.

Needed resources: The CALIPER Team in cooperation with the GEP WG were responsible for this action and drafted the framework for the “Post Doc Research Guide”, as well as implemented mini interviews for the framework’s assessment, in collaboration with the Committee of Postgraduate Studies and the top-level management. The action has been active for 7 months. The proposed framework has been submitted to the School’s top management for consideration.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: There is an ongoing discussion on the working condition of non-tenured researchers. It was decided to draft a proposal on the matter that given the circumstances could contribute to reaching a consensus and an officially endorsed framework.

Impact of the action: Drafting the framework for the Post Doc Research guide comprises a solid basis for discussion on the researchers’ working conditions on the topics which concern CALIPER. The achievement of a consensus and the adoption of a general framework is a work in progress beyond the scope of CALIPER.

The majority of the actions had never been attempted at the School before, and it was hard to estimate the correct overall timing of the actions. For this reason, a “stretch goal” approach was adopted. During this approach more activities were set to start/conclude within the 1st iteration, resulting in a more “front-loaded” GEP. This gave the opportunity to estimate the actions’ rate of progress, and then focus on work that would produce the most tangible results within the 1st iteration.

Institutional governance

Action 1: Collection of gender disaggregated data

Description/scope of the action: The action refers to the identification, preparation, and integration of specific questions into an annual anonymous questionnaire, in the framework of establishing procedures for the collection of gender aggregation data. It is expected that this information will support decision making in these areas.

Needed resources: This action required human resources such as the CALIPER Team, and the Communications Officer of the ECE NTUA (for the dissemination of the questionnaire on the official student’s forum and the School’s social media). Also, the Vice Dean was involved in the action, by sending the questionnaire to the School’s personnel mailing lists. The action has been active for 2 months and will continue.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The good collaboration between the CALIPER Team and the GEP WG, as well as the support of the top management, are the factors that enabled the implementation of this action. The action didn’t encounter any major challenges in its implementation

Impact of the action: The main objective of the action was to establish a data collection procedure. The action has reached its goals as the relevant questions have been established and integrated into the annual anonymous questionnaire. A second iteration of the questionnaire will take place the following year (May-June 2023).

Institutional communication

Action 1: Support the application of the “Guide to using non sexist language in administrative documents

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Description/scope of the action: The activity refers to the implementation of a training session regarding the application of the “Guide of using non sexist language in administrative documents”, which has been issued by the General Secretariat for Demography and Family Policy and Gender Equality, in March 2018. The main objective is to familiarise the School’s administrative personnel with the use of gender sensitive language and apply the Guide.

Needed resources: The CALIPER Team was fully involved in the implementation of the action, while the Head of Secretariat voluntarily offered her support and experience. Two persons from the Secretariat supported the CALIPER Team for the implementation of the action. The training was held online. The action needed 6 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The collaboration between the CALIPER Team and the Secretariat enabled the successful implementation of the action.

Impact of the action: The CALIPER team has produced training material and designed a training session on the use of gender-sensitive language in official documents. The particular [material](#) has been uploaded in the School’s official website.

Teaching and student services

Action 1: Integration of gender related topics in selected courses and lectures

Description/scope of the action: The action consisted of the integration of the gender related topics into selected courses and lectures. The main objective was to increase the awareness and make the curriculum more gender sensitive in general. Another goal of this action was to highlight the relevance and meaning of a gender approach in teaching and subsequently in research.

Needed resources: The GEP WG was involved in the identification of the courses, while the CALIPER team was involved in the preparation of the respective material and the follow up questionnaires. For each course that a gender related topic was integrated, a follow up questionnaire was prepared. Faculty members and researchers/teaching assistants participated in the discussions regarding the implementation of this activity. The action has been active for 11 months and will continue. It is not finalised as additional topics will be included in various courses in the 2nd year of the GEP.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The involvement of members of the CALIPER team in the teaching process enabled the preparation of the material. On the other hand, the CALIPER team faced a certain level of scepticism as regards the feasibility of integrating gender topics in courses that are entirely technical, and do not include managerial aspects.

Impact of the action: The CALIPER team produced relevant material for the undergraduate courses “Organisation and Management”, “Management systems” and “Energy Management and Environmental Policy” and the postgraduate course “Special Management Topics”. Some of the material was used in lectures during the winter and spring semesters.

Intersectionality

Action 1: Collection of gender equality data on intersectionality

Description/scope of the action: This action aimed at identifying key questions on gathering relevant intersectional data such as gender, religion, ethnicity, disabilities etc, to be integrated in the annual anonymous questionnaire, sent to all ECE NTUA personnel (academic, administrative, permanent researchers, technical staff), as well as to students (postgraduate and undergraduate).

Needed resources: The CALIPER Team with the GE WG were involved during the implementation of the particular action. Also, one person from the Communication Office was involved in the dissemination of the questionnaire on the official student's forum and the official social media of the ECE School. The vice Dean sent the questionnaire to the School's personnel mailing lists. The action has been active for 2 months and will continue.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: A factor that promoted the action was the good collaboration between the CALIPER Team and the GE WG, for the establishment of the respective questions. The expertise of the WG was used as some of its members had prepared questionnaires in the past, on various topics. No factors inhibited the action.

Impact of the action: The faculty established an intersectional questionnaire and integrated it into the [annual anonymous questionnaire](#), which has been published on the institutional website.

Collaborative actions

Action 1: Engagement of role models and dissemination activities

Description/scope of the action: The action referred to the implementation of a series of dissemination activities presenting positive role models. This action created a more gender friendly environment within the school, in order to achieve a more equal distribution between male & female students. Within the scope of this action a role model interview, and a coffee talk (interview - discussion with the role model and the students) took place.

Needed resources: The human resources that were needed was the CALIPER team, the GE WG and the Vice Dean, the role model, and technical communication staff of the ECE NTUA. The action has been active for 11 months and will continue.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: In particular, the fact that people from different disciplines actively supported the action enhanced its legitimacy and provided the relevant knowledge for its successful implementation. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: The main result is the successful implementation of 1 role model video and 1 coffee talk so far. In the coffee talk discussion 20 students took part (11 male and 9 female). The participants talked about the importance of role models, the importance of gender equality in entrepreneurship and startups, and the issue of glass ceiling in the field of start ups. Moreover, mini discussions with 5 young women took place, as regards the role model video impact, how it could influence a young person in choosing a STEM direction of studies / continuing studies in the STEM field / continuing a career in the STEM field, as well as future role models and topics that the respondents would like to see.

There were no significant problems in implementing awareness – raising events or even a training session for School staff. However, the structural actions require commitment from decision makers and the assignment of proper resources (human, financial, technical or otherwise) to actually implement the changes.

Action 2: WIN event

Description/scope of the action: The main objective of the event was to present experiences of women with a strong presence in innovation and entrepreneurship, highlight women-led innovations and develop strong links with the innovation and business environment.

Needed resources: The organisation and implementation of the WIN event was a collaborative process. At a School level, the GEP Working Group, the CALIPER Team and the Communication Office were involved, while at an Institutional level the GE Committee and the NTUA Career Office assisted in the dissemination process. Additionally, one person from the Communication Office was involved for the promotion of the event in the ECE NTUA official website and social media. A person from the ECE NTUA top management sent the invitations to all the ECE NTUA personnel. Finally, one person responsible for the event venue (the event was held at the Multimedia Auditorium of NTUA) supported the setting up of the equipment. The action needed 4 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The productive collaboration of the CALIPER team with the internal stakeholders that were involved, as well as the participation of the external stakeholders and members of the R&I Hub that contributed to the success of the event. The biggest challenge was the dissemination of the event to all of the School's students.

Actions that were implemented with the collaboration of the R&I Hub and/or the collaboration of the GE Committee and other departments at an Institutional level were observed to be relatively "easier". In these cases, it was possible to leverage external expertise (e.g. speakers, experts, etc.) to maximise their impact.

Impact of the action: The Women in Innovation (WIN) event took place on the 8th of April 2022. The event created more links with the innovation and business environment and the R&I Hub, while the number of participants was satisfactory.

3.2.1.5 Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB)

Made by CALIPER: Inspiring actions from IRB

In this section, the implemented actions of IRB will be presented, divided into the specific thematic areas of their GEP. During the first iteration phase, the actions that have been implemented belong to the areas of human resources, institutional governance, institutional communication, young scientists, sexual and gender harassment and collaborative actions. For each action, the briefing presents the *description of the action*, the *required resources*, the *key enabling factors* and the *main challenges*, and the *impact of the action*.

Human resources

Action 1: Review, update and disseminate existing recruitment policies and guidelines, assuring that the documentation has a gender sensitive approach.

Description/scope of the action: The focus of this action is to generate awareness and knowledge about adopting a more gender sensitive approach to existing department policies and guidelines, promoting a more gender-sensitive approach to human resources practice in general.

Needed resources: The members involved in the process were from the GEP WG for the coordination of the action, the Human Resources Department for the elaboration of the documentation, the Academic Office, and the HR Excellence in Research WG of IRB, responsible for the organisation of the relevant meetings for the realisation of this action and for giving feedback to the documentation as well as the final approval. The action needed 6 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: An important factor that contributed to the development of this action was a complementary institutional analysis done with the purpose of renewing the HR Excellence in research logo. This analysis also included the reviewing process of HR related documentation, allowing two

different working groups to provide better inputs, and feedback to the reviewing process of the existing human resources documentation.

Impact of the action: The development of this action provided a series of documents that serve as a backbone to all the institute's recruitment process and practices. The documents developed within the context of this action are shared with the Hiring Managers creating a broader knowledge of the recruitment measures, policies and protocols among the IRB Barcelona community.

Institutional governance

Action 1: Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader selection protocol

Description of the action: The main objective of the action is to promote the participation of female scientists in Group Leader recruitment processes. As an internal measure through the protocol, the overall idea is to increase awareness of the measures in the document, its advantages, and the results of its application.

Needed resources: The action was set in motion by the Human Resources department in collaboration with the CALIPER GEP WG for the coordination of the action and elaboration of the relevant documentation, and the directorate responsible for the approval of the protocol. The action needed 10 months to be finalised. The Protocol was recently used and implemented for a recent open call for Junior Group Leader.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The collaboration among the different internal stakeholders and direct involvement of the institute's directorate, was a significant facilitator of the action. No resistances were encountered in the implementation of this action.

Impact of the action: The fact that a call for Group Leader was opened during the elaboration and development of the present action, providing the ideal platform to share and consolidate the protocol with the involved stakeholders. In addition, the protocol itself was reviewed as one of the actions of the GEP, so this also provided a proper communication channel to promote the protocol and create awareness about its existence.

Institutional communication

Action 1: Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan

Description of the action: This action aimed at raising institutional awareness of existing and new efforts and initiatives to be implemented in matters pertaining to equality and diversity topics in the institute. The main objective in this action is to properly integrate a gender perspective at all levels of the organisation and all its policies. Within the context of this action presentations were held about the new GEP to the different departments, committees, and the institute's Faculty.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG planned, conducted and executed all of the presentation sessions of the GEP, in Collaboration with Fundraising and Communication Department (FUNCOM) and the Equality and Diversity Committee (EDC). The communications department supported to promote the events. A member of the Equality and Diversity Committee provided feedback and contributed to the communication material. The action needed 4 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The fact that many stakeholders (both internal and external) were engaged in the different activities of the CALIPER project, facilitated the successful implementation of the action. Even Though the “online meeting” modality served as a great tool, the period of time were the presentations were organised matched with the most important restrictions in regards to covid, this represented a challenge for the physical participation of some of the external stakeholders.

Impact of the action: The action increased the engagement of internal and external stakeholders and their interest towards the GEP. In total, a number of five sessions were conducted in order to present and provide visibility to the Gender Equality Plan. This action needed four months to be finalised.

Young scientists

Action 1: Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions

Description of the action: The action aims at providing to all the newcomers a general overview of efforts made at IRB Barcelona in matters pertaining to equality and diversity. The presentation explaining the new GEP and all the efforts in regard to equality and diversity has been included in the periodic induction session that is given to all the new employees and collaborators of the IRB Barcelona. As of July 2022, the presentation has been done two times, and it will continue as a recurring practice, planned and executed once a month going forward.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG, the HR department, the health and safety unit, and the EDC collaborated to plan and implement this action. The coordination of the presentation itself, involved the participation of members of the health and safety unit, which have the role of coordinating all the induction sessions. The action needed 10 months to be implemented.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: A factor that promoted the planning and execution of this action is the constant interaction through meetings and collaborations between the stakeholders involved.

Impact of the action: The action shows the efforts and initiatives of IRB related to equality and diversity, and the first onboarding session has already happened in June 2022.

Sexual and gender harassment

Action 1: Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment

Description of the action: The action aims at reviewing the existing workplace harassment protocol in the institution. The revision had two main objectives. The first one was simplifying the communication process and establishing the reference persons in case of activation of the protocol, the second priority was to update the document with the latest information including the local legal requirements. The protocol defines and includes the following types of harassment: Psychological harassment and discriminatory harassment, sexual harassment, harassment on the grounds of sex or sexual orientation and other types of discrimination. It also explains the conducts not considered harassment.

Needed resources: The involved stakeholders include: the CALIPER WG responsible for the development and coordination of the action, the Health and Safety Service and the HR department responsible for the coordination and elaboration of the document, the Fundraising, Communication and Marketing Department, in charge of the Translation of the document, the Health and Safety Committee and the Directorate to

organise the necessary meetings, feedback, and the Equality Commission for Reviewing and approving the whole process. The action needed ten months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The involvement of different stakeholders representing various commissions and members of different areas of the Institute has facilitated the action. The translation of the document in the official languages of the Institute represented an extra “time” challenge in the initial time frame set. There were no factors that inhibited the implementation of this action.

Impact of the action: The updated protocol is in place and has been announced to the IRB community by internal communication. The protocol is available on the institutional intranet.

Collaborative actions

Action 1: WIN event

Description of the action: The WIN event of IRB took place on the 14th of June. The overall idea and concept for the activity was to highlight the role of women in innovation, analysing different perspectives and points of view of women in different stages, positions and roles in the entrepreneur ecosystem and the factors that contribute to reaching their goals/objectives. IRB invited external stakeholders from its R&I Hub to participate as speakers.

Needed resources: The internal CALIPER WG was in charge of the organisation and coordination of the event. In addition, 1 member from the Directorate, 2 members from the Innovation Team of IRB, and 1 of the communication department collaborated with the working group in order to provide a better structure of the event. The action needed seven months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The collaboration among the different internal stakeholders and the interest of the external stakeholders to participate was a facilitating factor of the action. In addition the fact that the IRB has an internal Innovation department facilitated the planning and development of the event, specially for planning and engaging with external stakeholders.

Impact of the action: The event gave the opportunity to participants to share their information and personal experience and discuss future collaborations and cooperation. 50 people participated in the event.

3.2.1.6 Yasar University (YU)

Made by CALIPER: Inspiring actions from YU

One of the main bodies that have been created in the context of CALIPER, is the GEP working group (GEP WG), which acts as the steering and advisory body for the GEP implementation while the European Union Research Center team is responsible for the implementation of all the project phases. GEP working group includes 8 academics from various disciplines (social sciences and STEM departments) and 3 administrative staff members (high level and mid level).

In this section, the implemented actions of YU will be presented, divided into the specific thematic areas of their GEP. During the first iteration phase, the actions that have been implemented belong to the areas of institutional governance, research, sexual harassment and collaborative actions. For each action, the briefing presents the *description of the action*, the *required resources*, the *key enabling factors* and the *main challenges*, and the *impact of the action*.

Institutional governance

Action 1: Gender Equality body

Description/scope of the action: The action aimed at the establishment of a Gender Equality Body (GEB) as well as finalising its legal and operational structure. The GEB aims at raising internal and external gender equality awareness among students, staff members and external stakeholders through different activities.

Needed resources: GEB consists of a director, five executive board members and additional secretariat. The action was completed within the first iteration period.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The support of the top management facilitated the implementation of the action. There was no resistance reported.

Impact of the action: The gender equality body is established as a result of the work carried out within the framework of the CALIPER project. 15 events have been completed successfully since the establishment of the Body. Roundtable discussions with international female founders, and gender equality training to Yaşar Group are some of these events.

Action 2: Gender disaggregated data collection

Description/scope of the action: The action supports the gender disaggregated data collection. This action will enable the monitoring and the evaluation of the effectiveness of the gender equality policies in the institution, and the development of evidence-based policies for the promotion of gender equality in the institution.

Needed resources: The CALIPER Project Team and the top-management of the university collaborated for this action. The following organisational structure is involved for the successful completion of the action: Vice Rectorship for the Academic Affairs (Graduate School and all faculties), Vice Rectorship for Research and Innovation (European Union Research Center Directorate, Information and Technology Transfer Office Directorate, Project Support Office Directorate), Public Relations and Marketing Directorate, Human Resources Directorate, Library & Information Center Directorate, Student Affairs Directorate. The action needed 7 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Support and encouragement from the top management for the action has supported the initial implementation process. Moreover, the existing institutional reporting and quality management mechanisms will in the long run, ensure the continuous reporting of the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the action: The action established institutional gender-disaggregated data collection procedures having appointed relevant departments and units for the reporting processes.

Research

Action 1: Integration of gender into institutional strategic plan and institutional funding mechanisms

Description/scope of the action: The aim of the action is two-fold: 1. it aims to integrate the gender equality topic into the strategic planning 2. it aimed at the inclusion of the gender as a priority research area in the institutional funding mechanism. YU strategic plan includes objectives and indicators for research, education and awareness activities on gender equality. The gender dimension is in the process of being integrated in

the institutional funding mechanism, the scientific research fund (BAP) through the newly established research groups at the university.

Needed resources: Many people from the top and middle management of YU worked for the strategic plan and the institutional funding mechanism update. *Strategic plan:* Vice Rector for Legal and Administrative Affairs, Directorate of Graduate Education Institute, Faculty Deans, School Directorates, Research and Application Centers, Yaşar University Women's Studies Application and Research Center, Public Relations and Marketing Directorate, Media Center Directorate, Department of Media Relations. *Institutional funding:* Vice – Rector for Research and Innovation, Gender Studies Center, Researchers from various departments, External stakeholders. The action needed 10 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Support and encouragement from the top management for the action has promoted the initial implementation process. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the action: The action achieved the integration of measures and targets about gender to the institutional strategy of YU. The strategic plan of YU for 2020-2025 includes two strategic goals with specific targets and metrics on gender equality.

- 🔄 **STRATEGIC GOAL 4: SOCIAL CONTRIBUTION: Target 4.3:** Social integration for disadvantaged and under-represented groups. **Activities:** In-house regulations on gender equality and activities with stakeholders. **Metrics:** Number of on-site (physical) activities on gender awareness and equality Annual Target: 4, Number of distance (digital) activities on gender awareness and equality Annual Target: 10
- 🔄 **STRATEGIC GOAL 5: SUSTAINABILITY: Target 5.2:** To ensure social sustainability. **Activities:** Studies on gender equality, public institutions and external activities with stakeholders and preparation of relevant reports. **Metrics:** Number of activities and reports related to the Sustainable Development Goals, and report on the institutional performance.

Sexual harassment

Action 1: Creation of an international policy document

Description/scope of the action: The purpose of this document is to regulate the structure, mission and operating principles of Yaşar University Support Unit for Prevention of Gender-based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment, which was adopted by the Yaşar University Senate.

Needed resources: The Institutional policy document was prepared by the director of the Women & Family Studies Application and Research Center and approved by Yaşar University Rector and Board of Trustees. The action needed 11 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The cooperation of the director of the Women & Family Studies Application and Research Center with the university rector and the board of trustees contributed to the facilitation of the action implementation. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: The action is completed successfully with the development and adoption of a [policy document against sexism and sexual harassment](#).

Action 2: Gender based violence and sexual harassment prevention unit.

Description/scope of the action: The action concerned the establishment of gender-based discrimination, violence and sexual harassment prevention unit. Gender-based discrimination, violence and sexual harassment prevention unit is established within the scope of the institutional policy document that was prepared by the director of the Women & Family Studies Application and Research Center and approved by Yaşar University Rector.

Needed resources: For the implementation of this action, the director of the Women & Family Studies Application and Research Center and the Rector of YU were involved. The Unit has two bodies: the Coordinator and the Commission. The commission is made up of three academic members and one administrative member from the University. The action needed 11 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The support and willingness of the top management facilitated the process. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: The action is completed successfully with the approval of the policy document.

Collaborative actions

Action 1: WIN event

Description/scope of the action: The WIN Event aimed to raise awareness and attract more girls to STEM areas and highlight women's led innovations presenting startups and spin offs. The main target group of the event was female high school students from local schools.

Needed resources: Along with Yaşar University EU Center staff, a person from the Media Center, a staff from the Department of Public Relations, one staff from Department of Media Relations, and Director of the Career and Alumni Center were involved in the action. Furthermore, participation of the Rector in the event enabled high level representation and ownership. The action needed 15 months to be finalised.

WIN Event gathered the most attention during the first GEP iteration period. Students rated the event very high and indicated that they would like to take part in similar future events. According to them, the event enabled/increased students' knowledge about the place of women in science & innovation. Furthermore, the participants stated the positive impact the event had on their future career choices in STEM fields.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The collaboration between the YU and the members of the R&I Hub was a positive factor which contributed to the effective implementation of the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the action: The event organised on April 21st, 2022 and reached its goal, to increase awareness about STEM careers among female high school students, highlight women's led innovations presenting startups and spin offs, and create strong links among R&I Hub participants. The event gave the opportunity to participants to share their knowledge and personal experience and create further collaborations and cooperation between research and innovation. A total of 65 people attended the event, five teachers & speakers (all female), and 48 students (46 Female and 2 Not Specified).

3.2.1.7 Salento University (UNILE)

Made by CALIPER: Inspiring actions from UNILE

In this section, the implemented actions of UNILE will be presented, divided into the specific thematic areas of their GEP. During the first iteration phase, the actions that have been implemented belong to the areas of human resources, institutional governance, research, teaching and third mission, institutional communication, sexual harassment, and collaborative actions. For each action, the briefing presents the *description of the action*, the *required resources*, the *key enabling factors* and the *main challenges*, and the *impact of the action*.

Human resources

Action 1: To carry out activities in schools aimed at promoting a gender culture

Description of the action: The activity for the students was organised as an online meeting by the University of Salento to attract young girls to the STEM disciplines. The event promoted the orientation of secondary school students, in cooperation with the school structures, providing all the information necessary for an informed choice of university pathway, starting with the educational, scientific and professional options offered by the University of Salento.

Needed resources: The online meeting was planned and organised by the top and middle management of UNILE, and 3 academics, two from UNILE, and one from the University of Milano Bicocca. The action needed 2 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The willingness of the students to participate was a great facilitator of the action. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: Approximately 100 people among students and professors from different high schools attended the event. Most of the student participants demonstrated increased interest in STEM disciplines during the discussions.

Action 2: Promotion of actions to increase the visibility of doctoral students and young female researchers

Description of the action: Within the context of this action, an event for the promotion of visibility of female young students and researchers, was organised on the occasion of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science. The event was an opportunity to promote change and increase awareness and understanding of the role and importance of female figures in science. The participants were also informed about the procedure to acquire Post Doc Research grants through the university.

Needed resources: Both managerial and administrative departments, along with the GEP WG and the CALIPER team cooperated to implement this action. The PhD students of Mathematics and Physics supported by professors were the main actors for the implementation of the event. The action needed 2 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The excellent collaboration among the different internal stakeholders and the support from the relevant external stakeholders was a great facilitating element for the action. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: Fourteen people participated in the activity and were informed about how to acquire new Post Doc research grants.

Institutional governance

Action 1: Create a coordination group and build a dedicated team

Description/scope of the action: According to the "Vademecum for the development of the Gender Equality Plan in Italian Universities" universities are invited to identify a dedicated GEP Team for the implementation of their GEP, composed of more than one person, with specific expertise on gender issues (or adequately trained); it works in synergy with all the other structures of the institution with adequate resources, and is publicly supported by the top management of the institution. The same action was proposed at the University of Salento. The GEP Team was defined and developed the GEP University Plan. This law functioned as a facilitator to the overall implementation of the GEP at UNILE.

Needed resources: Overall 11 people for the implementation of the action were involved. The Group was nominated by the Academic Senate on the basis of a Rector proposal. The Rector was also providing financial resources for supporting the activities of the GEP Team and favouring the GEP implementation, as well as for creating a prize for the best female researcher of the year to women researchers who have particularly distinguished themselves and a prize for the best doctoral thesis written by a young researcher from the University. The action needed 2 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The willingness of the Senate to implement and coordinate the action was a facilitating factor. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: A dedicated GEP Team was appointed by the University Governance bodies and is monthly convened by the Rector, who is also the coordinator of the Team.

Research, teaching, and third mission

Action 1: Interdisciplinary seminars on gender issues and feasibility study about the introduction of a gender course

Description/scope of the action: An Interdisciplinary network was created for implementing the UnisalentoPLUS initiative, which is devoted to disseminating an inter- and transdisciplinary teaching approach in the study courses of the UNILE on topics considered strategic such as: gender issues, sustainable development, peace and human rights, inequalities and racism. A choral project, the aim of which is to define additional pathways to the ordinary didactic offer in order to provide students with tools for in-depth reflection on issues and topics whose complexity can only be tackled from an inter- and trans-disciplinary perspective.

Needed resources: The "Questioni di genere" ("gender issues ") network, coordinated by the Rector's delegate for gender policies, collects all the academic staff involved in the organisation of the interdisciplinary seminars about gender issues. The network consists of around 60 people. The action needed 16 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The collaboration of the UnisalentoPLUS with the CALIPER team facilitated the action.

Impact of the action: The high level of participation in the initiatives demonstrates the interest in the topics covered and the increased sensitivity towards gender equality policies. The impact of the action is demonstrated by participants' recruitments (more than 500 participants in 8 seminars).

Institutional communication

Action 1: Create and Update the University website a web page dedicated to the activities of the Vice-Rector for Gender Policies with documents, regulations, and news on initiatives and actions in progress related to gender policies

Description/scope of the action: The institutional page is the main tool to make more visible the activities in place for Gender Policies and all the related initiatives. It is also fundamental to give support in case of mobbing or sexual harassment.

Needed resources: Two professors, 1 postdoc and 3 Administrative/Technicians were involved in the set-up process. The action needed 2 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The great collaboration among the different internal stakeholders was a key factor in the action. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: The special section at the University's websites have been created. The action achieved to raise awareness regarding the gender equality policies within the institution.

Gender policy: <https://www.unisalento.it/ateneo/politiche-di-genere?open=2>

GEP: <https://www.unisalento.it/documents/20143/3500738/GEP22-25.pdf>

Sexual harassment

Action 1: Publicising and informing about the rules and the role of the CUG (Comitato unico di Garanzia – joint guarantee committee) and of the Ombudsperson and access to their services.

Description/scope of the action: This action aims at spreading awareness of these phenomena within a very large and articulated academic community. The Ombud Person will be responsible for handling all the cases of sexual harassment as an external collaborator.

Needed resources: The Academic Senate oversaw this action. They held informative meetings and created dedicated contact channels and rules. The action needed 16 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The willingness of the Academic Senate to coordinate the action was a great facilitator for this action. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: The Ombudsperson has been appointed, leading to the creation of a mechanism where harassment, bullying and discrimination cases can be reported to.

Collaborative actions

Action 1: WIN event

Description/scope of the action: The WIN event aimed at introducing excellent researchers who deal with innovation and who have won international awards on research projects and also women entrepreneurs who work by promoting a gender policy within their actions.

Needed resources: In terms of human resources the GEP WG of the institution was in charge of the implementation of this activity.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The willingness of the external stakeholders to attend as speakers was a factor that facilitated the event. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: The event was held on 21st of May 2022. The participants were students, external stakeholders and researchers. The online audience was about 30 people. It will continue next year.

3.2.2. Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)

3.2.2.1 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG)

Made by CALIPER: Inspiring actions from SRNSFG

One of the main bodies that have been created in the context of CALIPER, is the GEP working group (GEP WG) that includes staff from different departments of the Foundation, such as Science department, Law and Administration department, office of International Relations and Fundraising which is responsible for the implementation of all the project phases.

In this section, the implemented actions of SRNSFG will be presented, divided into the specific thematic areas of their GEP. During the first iteration phase, the actions that have been implemented belong to the areas of human resources, institutional governance, institutional communication, sexual harassment, intersectionality, and collaborative actions. For each action, the briefing presents the *description of the action*, the *required resources*, the *key enabling factors* and the *main challenges*, and the *impact of the action*.

Human resources

Action 1: Training for the staff involved in recruitment process

Description of the action: The action included the organisation of a training for SRNSFG's staff involved in the recruitment process. Main objective of the action was to raise awareness about gender equality for combating gender bias in recruitment.

Needed resources: The CALIPER GEP WG was responsible for the implementation of the action. In particular, 2 people of the WG were in charge of the action, they identified content and prepared the relevant materials. The action needed 6 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Collaboration among the GEP WG members, their expertise and willingness, enabled the successful implementation of the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the action: The action raised awareness about gender equality and ensured that every person involved in the recruitment process is aware of gender related issues, discrimination and stereotypes. Overall, six key recruiting personnel were trained.

Action 2: Informational brochure/guide for recruited staff about gender equality

Description of the action: The action included the elaboration of the informational brochure/guide for recruited staff about gender equality. Main objective of the action is raising awareness about gender equality and ensuring that every person who starts working at Foundation is aware of gender-related issues.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG and the Law and Administration department collaborated for the implementation of the action. One person of the WG and two people of the department of Law and Administration were in charge of the action. The WG covered more the role of elaborating and designing the brochure, while the Law and Administration department had a crucial role in the concrete implementation of the action. No additional resources or equipment was required during the implementation. The brochure was prepared in electronic format. The action needed 1 month to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Collaboration between the GEP WG and the department of Law and Administration represented a factor which definitely promoted the implementation of the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the action: The brochure has been prepared and ready to be used (<https://rustaveli.org.ge/res/docs/11745b5bb281c1f532ffe0c385289fe9520a8e8b.pdf>).

Action 3: Development of an exit questionnaire

Description of the action: The action consisted of the development of exit questionnaire for staff in order to understand the reasons why employees leave the organisation from a gender perspective.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG and the Law and Administration department collaborated for the implementation of the action. In particular, 1 person of the WG and two people of the department of Law and Administration were in charge of the action. The WG covered more the role of elaborating and designing the exit questionnaire, while the Law and Administration department had an important role in the structure of the questionnaire. Also, Law and Administration department will support the sustainability of the action and integrate it as a permanent process for the people leaving the department. The action needed 1 month to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Collaboration between the GEP WG and the Law and Administration department promoted the implementation of the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the action: The exit questionnaire is integrated in the institution's working procedures.

Action 4: Provision of different training and activities improving professional skills

Description of the action: The action included the provision of two different training and activities aiming at the provision of significant career support for the improvement of staff professional skills. Main objective of

the action is to provide career support for all employees from different departments, focusing on the Science department.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG members collaborated for the implementation of the action. Each training required its materials and equipment and organisation details. The action needed 9 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Collaboration between the GEP WG and different departments, such as the Science department and Office of International Relations and Fundraising of the Foundation represented a factor which facilitated the action. The only barrier was the COVID-19 pandemic, which limited the training opportunities for this period since less training was organised due to restrictions on gatherings and events.

Impact of the action: In the first training there were 12 participants from the Science Department and Office of International Relations and Fundraising. In the second training there were 2 participants from the Science Department and the Department of Finance and Economics. Overall, the action improved the professional skills of the Foundation's staff and increased the number of professional opportunities for female participants from different departments.

Institutional governance

Action 1: Collecting gender disaggregated data on the organisation institutional level

Description of the action: The action included collecting gender disaggregated data at the institutional level, via questionnaires which were distributed at the SRNSFG staff. Main objective of the action is to raise awareness about the gender equality status within the organisation.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG and the Law and Administration department jointly implemented the action. Two people of the WG and two people of the department of Law and Administration were in charge of the action. Meanwhile the GEP WG members were actively involved to elaborate a questionnaire and distribute it among the top management and staff of SRNSFG to monitor and set actions effectiveness. The action needed 1 month to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The main pillar of implementation of this action was the collaboration between WG and the Law and Administration Department of SRNSFG. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the action: The action was successfully implemented. Special mechanism for collecting and analysing gender disaggregated data was created. Therefore, data were collected, analysed and presented to the top management.

Action 2: Modifying existing job description in the administration unit of SRNSFG, by adding targeted functions towards gender neutral language

Description of the action: As there was not any gender related duties/functions in SRNSFG before, this action aimed to set and hand targeted functions to the responsible person in the Law and Administrative Department of SRNSFG. Functions, set by this action envisages to ensure implementing regular gender balance monitoring of SRNSFG staff, its analyses, presentation to the top management and indication in the

annual report of SRNSFG, as well as organising targeted meetings, including with top management, in order to discuss gender issues in the organisation.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG and the Law and Administration department jointly implemented the action. 2 persons of the WG and 1 person of the department of Law and Administration were in charge of the action. There are no additional resources to implement this action and won't be necessary either in the future. The action needed 1 month to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The main pillar of implementation of this action was the collaboration between WG and Law and Administration Department of SRNSFG. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the action: As part of the action, Targeted functions/duties were set and handed to the responsible person in the Law and Administration Department. As a result, implementing regular gender balance monitoring in the organisation, relevant reports, discussion with top management and organising targeted meetings for discussing gender related meetings will be ensured. These functions were added in the job description of targeted person in the Law and Administration Department of SRNSFG, on the basis of the Decree of Director General of the foundation - 30.09.2021 N127.

Institutional communication

Action 1: Elaborate a strategy encompassing measures/actions related to the institutional communication enhancement regarding gender equality

Description of the action: The communication strategy defines the activities which enable the organisation of public events, workshops, seminars, special training. Almost every activity involves several institutional bodies within SRNSFG. The communication strategy describes specific measures and initiatives that will contribute to the establishment of gender-sensitive communication.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG and PR Office collaborated on the implementation of the action. In particular, 2 persons of the WG and 1 person of PR Office were in charge of the action. Communication strategy was approved by Top Management. The action needed 10 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The great collaboration among the different stakeholders facilitated the implementation of the action. No factors inhibited the action.

Impact of the action: As result of the action, a communication strategy was developed which includes particular actions and activities for the promotion of gender equality.

Action 2: Create a special section on the SRNSFG website revealing successful Georgian women in STEM/research

Description of the action: A special section dedicated to women in science has been created in SRNSFG website to raise awareness about women being successful in their professional life.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG, the Office of International Relations and Fundraising, the PR Office, and the Office of International Relations and Fundraising identified the target audience from different

stakeholders and gathered the information for the section. The PR office disseminated and promoted information about the female researchers. The action needed 4 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The great collaboration among the CALIPER WG, Office of International Relations and Fundraising, PR Office The Office of International Relations and Fundraising was a facilitator. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: The [special section](#) has been created and is a work in progress. The action achieved to raise awareness among societies on women's engagement in STEM and general in science.

Action 3: to design and implement a strategic communication plan based on all aspects that could motivate all internal/external stakeholders to become active participants in developing institutional communication

Description of the action: This action aimed to design and implement a strategic communication plan based on all aspects that could motivate all internal/external stakeholders to become active participants in developing institutional communication.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG and PR Office collaborated for the implementation of the tasks related to action. Communication plan was approved by Top Management. The action needed 10 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The great collaboration between the CALIPER WG and PR Office was a facilitator. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: The action set and implemented a special targeted plan streaming to cooperate in all aspects, developed efficient communication process between institutions and established a sustainable and efficient ground for Georgian STEM eco-system.

Research funding

Action 1: Checking the existence of gender balance in research teams at the project registration stage

Description of the action: This action aimed at implementing gender balance control mechanism through Grant Management Unified Electronic System (GMUS) by creating a control field in the system, where project Principal Investigators fill information about the exact number of female/male researchers in their team.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG closely collaborated with the Department of Administration and Law and IT Office of the foundation. Two members from the GEP WG supervised the whole process of creating gender balance checking mechanism. The action needed 7 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Collaboration between the GEP WG, the department of Law and Administration and IT office represented a factor which promoted the implementation of the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the action: This action is now implemented for one scientific grant call - Joint Call of the Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia and the National Research Council Italy (CNR).

Action 2: Establishing award for female scientists

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Description of the action: This action aimed at establishing an annual award for women scientists working in the field of informational technologies; to disseminate their research work and acknowledge their efforts. It introduces successful women scientists to the wider community in Georgia aiming at leading to positive changes in attitudes towards women scientists.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG closely collaborated with the Department of Administration and Law of the Foundation. One member from the GEP WG supervised the whole process of establishing award for female scientists in Georgia. Since the process of establishing award for female scientists required additional financial resources, CALIPER WG with close collaboration of SRNSFG staff carried out specific activities to allocate funds. CALIPER WG with close collaboration of SRNSFG staff and external stakeholders elaborated terms of reference of the award and announced award grant call for successful female researchers. The action needed 6 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Close collaboration between the GEP WG members on one hand and with the Department of Administration and Law on the other, contributed to establishing specific gender related guidelines and a smooth run of the implementation process of the action. The only factor that inhibited the process was related to the fact that the selection of the evaluation committee took longer than it was expected.

Impact of the action: The award for female scientists was established. The action will be continued in the future.

Action 3: Providing evaluators/committee members gender related guidelines

Description/scope of the action: At SRNSFG there were no guidelines on gender stereotypes and unconscious bias to evaluators. This action aimed at introducing evaluators/committee members to specific guidelines and training on gender stereotypes and unconscious bias.

Needed resources: The action was implemented by two GEP WG members in close cooperation with the Department of Administration and Law.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Close collaboration between the GEP WG members on one hand and with the Department of Administration and Law on the other, contributed to creating specific gender related guidelines and a smooth run of the implementation process of the action. The main factor that inhibited the process was related to the fact that revising the final version of the guidelines by the department of Administration and Law took longer than it was expected.

Impact of the action: The guidelines will help the evaluators adopt a more bias and stereotype free perspective, making the whole process more transparent.

Sexual harassment

Action 1: Adopt a sexual harassment policy

Description/scope of the action: This action aimed at elaborating SRNSFG's Sexual Harassment Policy. It consisted of developing and adopting the written policy prohibiting harassment including sexual harassment. The action provides the adopted policy document to all employees of the foundation including internal meetings on the issue of workplace sexual harassment.

Needed resources: The action was completely implemented by the one GEP WG member in close cooperation with the Department of Administration and Law, which was mainly in charge of revising the policy document in terms of legal issues as well as workplace operations. The action needed 6 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Close collaboration between the GEP WG members and the Department of Administration and Law, contributed to the successful execution of the action.

Impact of the action: The sexual harassment policy has been adopted.

Action 2: Establish a Mechanism for Reporting sexual harassment incidents

Description/scope of the action: This action aimed at establishing a mechanism for reporting; designating an appropriate individual to whom an employee of the foundation could make a complaint; and encouraging employees to report harassment.

Needed resources: One employee from the Department of Administration and Law was designated as an individual to whom the SRNSFG staff now can make complaints. At every internal meeting, one member of the WG who was responsible for supervising the actions related to sexual harassment, paid special attention to the complaints procedure component of the policy in order to make this latter more effective. The action needed 6 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Close collaboration between the GEP WG members and the Department of Administration and Law, contributed to the successful execution of the action.

Impact of the action: The reporting mechanism that addressing sexual harassment incidents in the workplace is in place.

Intersectionality

Action 1: Gather disaggregated data by gender in conjunction with ethnicity, gender identity, age, disability, religion, etc.

Description/scope of the action: The action consisted of the establishment of the reporting system of disaggregated data collection with the view of raising the awareness about an intersectional approach as a part of gender equality and antidiscrimination policy at the institutional level.

Needed resources: The reporting system was elaborated by the WG member in charge of the given activity. In order to ensure its relevance for the nature of the Institution, it was closely reviewed with a member of the Science Department who is also a member of CALIPER WG. The action needed 7 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Close collaboration between the GEP WG members and willingness of the Foundation employees to get engaged in the process, contributed to the successful launch and implementation of the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation process itself.

Impact of the action: The ready-made survey collects sex disaggregated data in conjunction with other intersecting identities for the staff of the Institution. The survey has already been sent to the employees of

the institution and the first responses have been submitted. Overall, the response is encouraging. The institution will continue working on the dissemination of the survey to increase the responses.

Collaborative actions

Action 1: To elaborate ToR for Annual Female Scientists Award with academia and universities

Description/scope of the action: This action aimed at establishing an award for women scientists working in the field of informational technologies; encouraging women scientists and research activities, annually introducing successful women scientists to the wider community in Georgia and to lead to positive changes in attitudes towards women scientists. The action is already implemented, CALIPER WG with close collaboration of SRNSFG staff and external stakeholders elaborated Terms of Reference (ToR) of the award and announced award grant call for successful female researchers.

Needed resources: Since the process of establishing award for female scientists required additional financial resources CALIPER WG with close collaboration of SRNSFG staff carried out specific activities in order to allocate funds in the budget of the SRNSFG for administering the reward for female scientists as well as to compile grant call documentation and evaluation criteria. The action needed 6 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Close collaboration between the GEP WG members on one hand and with the Department of Administration and Law on the other, contributed to establishing specific gender related guidelines and a smooth run of the implementation process of the action. The main factor that inhibited the process was related to the fact that the selection of evaluation committee took longer that it was expected.

Impact of the organisation: This action raised the visibility of female researchers in the Georgian research and academic community and promoted their work.

Action 2: Providing evaluators/committee members gender related guidelines

Description/scope of the action: This action aimed at introducing evaluators/committee members with specific guidelines and training on gender stereotypes, unconscious bias; training of all evaluators/committee members in accordance with specific training materials and guidelines and to ensure successful evaluation process without any kind of gender bias.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG closely collaborated with the Department of Administration and Law of the foundation in order to effectively elaborate the above-mentioned guidelines. 2 members from the GEP WG supervised the whole process of compiling gender related special guidelines for evaluators and committee members. The action needed 10 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Close collaboration between the GEP WG members on one hand and with the Department of Administration and Law on the other, contributed to creating specific gender related guidelines and a smooth run of the implementation process of the action. The main factor that inhibited the process was related to the fact that revising final version of the guidelines by the department of Administration and Law took longer that it was expected.

Impact of the organisation: This action increased awareness of evaluators/committee members on gender related issues and can ensure gender bias free evaluation procedures.

Action 3: Collaboration in the process of creating gender dimension in the evaluation criteria for the future grant calls

Description/scope of the action: This action aimed at implementing gender balance control mechanism by creating a control field in the system, where project PI's fill information about the exact number of female/male researchers in their team.

Needed resources: The CALIPER WG closely collaborated with the Department of Administration and Law and IT Office of the foundation in order to effectively implement the above-mentioned action. 2 members from the GEP WG supervised the whole process of creating gender balance checking mechanism. However, the group itself was fully engaged in every step of implementing the given action. The action needed 5 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: Collaboration between the GEP WG, the department of Law and Administration and IT office represented a factor which promoted the implementation of the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the organisation: This action creates a gender balance control mechanism in scientific teams at the project registration stage to be implemented eventually in all grant calls

Action 4: WIN event

Description/scope of the action: The WIN event aimed to highlight and value women's led innovations presenting start-ups and raising awareness. The main objective of the event was to encourage young female researchers for building STEM career in Business, to demonstrate role models and future possibilities in STEM by popularising and promoting mobility of young female researchers between research and industry.

Needed resources: Five persons of the CALIPER WG and 1 person from the science popularisation department were in charge of the event. The action needed 4 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The willingness of the internal and external stakeholders to cooperate was a facilitating factor for the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the organisation: The WIN event was organised on 30th of April onsite, with 52 participants. The event gave the opportunity to participants to share their information and personal experience among other participants and also make a start for future collaborations and cooperation. The continuation of the action (to organise WIN events in the future) will further improve the results in terms of more collaboration and cooperation between research and innovation.

Action 5: Organise with joint efforts special targeted events, conference, symposia, e.g. in the frame of "Science Fest" one conference dedicated for Georgian Female Researchers

Description/scope of the action: On 20/11/21, SRNSFG organised an international conference "Women in Science" within the framework of the 2021 Science Festival and the EU Research and Innovation Framework Program "Horizon 2020". The event was attended by female scientists working in STEM directions of various higher education institutions and scientific-research institutes of Georgia. The main goal of the event was to emphasise the role of the female researchers for science development and their contribution for social benefits and well-being.

Needed resources: The Office of International Relations and Fundraising, the PR office, and the Science Department organised the event. The action needed 1 month to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The willingness of the organisational team was a facilitating factor for the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the organisation: The action increased SRNSFG institutional communication capacities on gender equality issues.

Action 6: To share information related to women for their popularisation on SRNSFG webpage and social media

Description/scope of the action: A special section woman in science has been created in SRNSFG website. The website serves to make Georgian women popular at the initial stage of their career and to showcase the famous Georgian female scientists telling success stories about their career. The section represents female researchers coming from all fields of science including Humanities as well.

Needed resources: CALIPER WG, Office of International Relations and Fundraising, PR Office The Office of International Relations and Fundraising identified the target audience from different stakeholders and got the information. The PR office disseminated and promoted the information about the female researchers. The action needed 10 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The great collaboration among different departments was a facilitating factor for the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the organisation: The action increased SRNSFG institutional communication capacities on gender equality issues.

Action 7: To develop institutional communication with the aim to harmonise the STEM system

Description/scope of the action: A special section woman in science has been created in SRNSFG website. The website serves to make Georgian women popular at the initial stage of their career and to showcase the famous Georgian female scientists telling success stories about their career. The section represents female researchers coming from all fields of science including Humanities as well.

Needed resources: CALIPER WG, Office of International Relations and Fundraising, PR Office The Office of International Relations and Fundraising identified the target audience from different stakeholders and got the information. The PR office disseminated and promoted the information about the female researchers. The action needed 10 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The great collaboration among different departments was a facilitating factor for the action. There have been no factors that inhibited the implementation.

Impact of the organisation: The action increased SRNSFG institutional communication capacities on gender equality issues.

3.2.2.2 Executive Unit for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania (UEFISCDI)

Made by CALIPER: Inspiring actions from UEFISCDI

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

In this section, the implemented actions of UEFISCDI will be presented, divided into the specific thematic areas of their GEP. During the first iteration phase, the actions that have been implemented belong to the areas of institutional communication, innovation ecosystems and collaborative actions. For each action, the briefing presents the *description of the action*, the *required resources*, the *key enabling factors* and the *main challenges*, and the *impact of the action*.

Institutional communication

Action 1: Development of an informative kit on gender sensitive communication

Description/scope of the action: The action consists of the development of an informative kit with the aim of raising awareness on the importance of using gender sensitive language and how to recognise and avoid gender stereotypes.

Needed resources: The informative kit was developed by the GEP WG. The team carried out extensive research on gender sensitive communication kits and best practice examples. One person from the Communication department provided support to the WG in adjusting protocols for internal and external communication. The action needed 9 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: The great collaboration between the GEP WG and the communication department represented a facilitating factor. There were no factors or barriers hindering implementation.

Impact of the action: The main result of the action is the development of the informative kit.

Innovation ecosystems

Action 1: Implementing quotas/targets for women participation in panels

Description/scope of the action: The action established quotas/targets in speaker panels at events organised by UEFISCDI. A target of at least 50% was set for women's participation as speakers.

Needed resources: The action was implemented by the GEP WG, with input from other UEFISCDI staff. Moreover, the WG was in charge of all preparatory actions related to the actual organisation of events, including the drafting of the concepts and agendas, nominating and inviting speakers, drafting and sending invitations to potential participants, and promoting the event online. Support was provided by one person from the communication department to promote the events via institutional channels. The action needed 7 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: In establishing quotas, the GEP WG benefitted from the full support of both middle and top management. There were no factors that inhibited the implementation

Impact of the action: The target for the 50% female representation in panels of various events is set and achieved.

Collaborative actions

Action 1: WIN event

Description/scope of the action: The event focused on Gender Mainstreaming in Responsible Research and Innovation. There were invited speakers with different background (creative industries, tech companies, science parks, RPOs) to discuss about the intersections between gender equality and responsible innovation.

Needed resources: Overall 4 people from the GEP WG were involved. Also, a person of the communication department was involved in order to disseminate/promote the event via institutional channels (e.g. website, social media etc.). The action needed 5 months to be finalised.

Key enabling factors and main challenges: External stakeholders were involved both as speakers and as participants. The collaboration with them was a facilitating factor of the activity. No resistance was reported.

Impact of the action: The event was attended by 50 participants, out of which approximately 25 were external to UEFISCDI (researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, representatives of NGOs etc.). The event promoted an increased involvement of women in the innovation ecosystem, both by ensuring a balanced representation of women as speakers in panels as well as by addressing Gender mainstreaming in responsible research and innovation.

4. Conclusion and next steps

This deliverable was the second policy briefing out of the three the CALIPER project will develop. It provides with recommendations on the implementation of an inclusive GEP, drawing upon the knowledge generated during the first iteration phase of the project related to the gender equality actions that the RPOs/RFOs have been implementing and which were included in their GEP. It contains suggestions both in terms of methodology, as well as practical advice on how to execute concrete actions.

The third briefing will contain concrete information based on the CALIPER experience from the evaluation phase and will take into account evidence and results of the first iteration phase as well as the refinement process and the results of the whole monitoring and evaluation phase.

